

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B283
Date: 16 April 2007
Take Off: 15:53:00
Landing: 20:59:30
Flight Time: 5h06m30

Campaign: IASI - ARIES

Operating Area: Ellington - Oklahoma

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	SWS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
11	MARSS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
12	AMS 1	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
13	AMS 2	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
14	Mission Scientist 3	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B283 Track 16-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B283
 Date: 16/4/07
 Project: IASI
 Location: Ellington Airfield, Houston

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
141759		Start-Up	-.24 kft	358	29'36.06N 95'10.05W
154549		ASP	-.25 kft	006	Open for take off
155300		T/O	-.25 kft	178	
165956		Video	19.7 kft	336	FFC1 and UFC1
170755	170945	Profile 1	8.8 - 6.8 kft	046	
171127	171336	Profile 1.2	6.8 - 4.8 kft	236	Q3017 or q1022 5000ft
171556	171808	Profile 1.3	4.7 - 2.5 kft	075	
171808	174101	Run 1	2.5 kft	040	17:18:41 start
174545	181216	Run 1.2	2.5 kft	182	2700ft S to N
175426		Video	2.5 kft	182	FFC 1 switched to DFC
181550	182715	Run 1.3	2.0 kft	349	2200ft N to S
182824	182921	Run 1.4	2.0 - 2.1 kft	114	
183300	184625	Run 1.5	2.0 kft	197	18:33
185140	190648	Profile 2	2.0 - 16.8 kft	004	
191508	191739	Profile 2.2	16.8 - 19.0 kft	192	
191843	193511	Profile 2.3	19.0 - 33.0 kft	187	
194057		Video	33.0 kft	337	DFC switched to UFC
194113	194432	Profile 2.4	33.0 - 35.0 kft	344	
194432	195418	Run 2	35.0 kft	352	
194445		Sonde	35.0 kft	352	
194543		Sonde 2	35.0 kft	351	
194716		Sonde 3	35.0 kft	352	
194952		Sonde 4	35.0 kft	352	
195841	201422	Run 2.2	35.0 kft	179	
195855		Sonde 5	35.0 kft	184	
200543		Sonde 6	35.0 kft	189	
201832	203057	Run 2.3	35.1 - 35.0 kft	351	S to N
203623	205125	Profile 3	35.0 - 14.2 kft	191	
205930		Land	1.1 kft	177	Will Rogers Oklahoma
210106		ASP	1.2 kft	356	closed
210422		PAN Oklahoma	1.2 kft	178	35'24.03N 97'36.16W
221503		Start-Up	1.2 kft	178	35'24.03N 97'36.15W
221511		ASP	1.2 kft	178	Opened
221928		T/O	1.2 kft	179	From Oklahoma
233746		Land	-.14 kft	176	Ellington
234000		ASP	-.13 kft	179	closed
234135		final	-.13 kft	178	29'36.06N 95'10.06W

B283 Track 16-APR-07

Sortie Brief

Flight B283

Mon 16th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Stuart Newman

Briefing: 0845L

Take off: 1045L

Land: 1600L at Oklahoma

Land: 1830L at Houston

Aim: To underfly AIRS on AQUA satellite, performing radiation measurements and measuring the state of the atmosphere over ARM instrument site. The overpass is at 1951 UTC (1451 L)

Location: Over ARM instrument site located near Lamont, Oklahoma.

Weather conditions: Predominantly clear skies.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions crossing ARM site south-north.

Fixed point South: (35°50' N, 97°36.8' W)

Fixed point Centre: (36°35' N, 97°36' W)

Fixed point North: (37°20'N, 97° 35'W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to ARM site area to arrive at point Sth at low level (2700 ft) (90 mins)
2. SLR Sth to Nth at 2700 ft (30 mins)
3. SLR Nth to Sth at 2700 ft (30 mins)
4. Profile ascent from 2700 ft to 6000 ft followed by SLR at 6000 ft under Vance MOA, followed by profile ascent to approx. FL120 (30 mins)
5. Profile ascent to FL300 Nth to Sth (20 mins)
6. Profile ascent from Sth towards Nth to FL350 followed by SLR at FL350 finishing at point Nth (20 mins)
7. SLR Nth to Sth at FL350, launching sondes as required (20 mins)
8. SLR Sth to Nth at FL350, launching sondes as required (20 mins)
(7. or 8. to coincide with overpass at 1951Z, 1451L; for the overpass run request launch of 4 sondes in quick succession in advance of overpass time, for other SLR request launch of 2 sondes during run.)
9. Profile descent Nth to Sth from FL350 to approx. FL110 (25 mins)
10. Zigzag descent to minimum altitude between point Sth and MOA boundary (15 mins)
11. Recover to Oklahoma City (15 mins) – total sortie time 315 mins
12. Refuel at Oklahoma (60mins)
13. Take off and transit to Houston (90mins)

Mission scientist's debrief for JAIVEx flight B283 on 16 April 2007

S. M. Newman

Summary:

Decent clear sky conditions for AIRS validation over land
Useful collocated AIRS, ARIES, S-HIS and NAST-I radiance observations
ARM site ground-based profile measurements in close proximity

Following a transit from Houston the FAAM 146 profiled down to commence low-level runs north-south over the Oklahoma ARM site passing just west of the central facility. Satellite imagery had shown a band of cirrus advecting in from the south, but the first runs at 2700 feet were clear at all levels. ARIES observed the changing emission properties when viewing in the nadir. Shorter runs north-south and a run to the ARM central point and back were also performed at 2200 feet, coinciding with the WB-57 arriving at FL570 on the same track heading north. By the end of the 146's southward leg at 2200 feet the cirrus had just started encroaching overhead.

The FAAM 146 ascended in a stepped profile to FL350, which was complicated by the need to ascend to through the Vance MOA military airspace and manoeuvres necessitated by air traffic control. FL350 was reached shortly before the Aqua overpass at 1952Z with the 146 positioned close to the ARM site heading north. Four sondes were released and timed to be airborne during the overpass time (when the 146 had neared the northern end of its track and the WB-57 was positioned over the ARM site). Both aircraft continued to follow the track with two further runs at FL350 completed by the 146 (two further sondes were released). ARIES on FAAM 146 and S-HIS and NAST-I on WB-57 continued to record radiances of the scene. By this time the cirrus was extensive over the southern half of the track, at altitudes below FL350, though with enough clearances to make continuing worthwhile. The 146 conducted a profile descent on approach to Oklahoma City for refuelling.

The combination of partially clear sky conditions with AIRS, FAAM 146 and WB-57 measurements co-aligned should produce some useful results from this sortie.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN

JAVEX - OKLAHOMA

Flight No **B.283**

Date **16/4/2007**

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1553		TAKE-OFF			
1616	Transit	FL240	336	31°16'/96W	In high RH air, small crystals
1642	"	"	335	33°35'/96W	Extensive high level cloud
1700	Descending	FL195	336	33°6'/97°30'	Wispy Ci
170755	P1 ↓	FL090	Turn	35°42'/97°36'	Has cleared overhead!
170945	interrupt	FL070			Turning, holding pattern
171127	P1.2 ↓	"			Recommence
171336	interrupt	5000'		35°42'/97°48'	Hi Ci to south
1	P1.3 ↓	5000'		35°42'/97°36'	Hazy on horizon
171841	R1.1	2700'	350	35°48'/97°36'	4000 ↑ 6000 PCASP
1726	"				clear skies above, bit hazy horizon
1733	"	2700'	358	35°48'/97°30'	Fields, few wooded areas
174101	end R1.1	"		37°18'/97°30'	Still clear overhead
174545	R1.2	2700'	183	37°18'/97°30'	North to South
1757	"	"			Higher cloud visible ahead to south
1807	"	"	181		Still clear above
180930	"	"	182	35°34'/97°30'	Just coming under high cloud at Sth point
181216	end R1.2	"			
181550	R1.3	2200'	002	36°54'/97°30'	
182715	end R1.3	"			
182824	R1.4	2200'	117		Heading for ARM
182921	end R1.4	"			(mini ARM run)
183300	R1.5	"	188		Run South, clear above
1840	"	"	179	36°6'/97°36'	Ci coming overhead
184625	end R1.5	"			Extensive Ci at this S. end

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.283**...

 Date **16/4/2007**...

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
185140	P2.1	2200' ↑			Allowed to push thru' MOA
1913	FL170	— holding pattern			as required by air traffic control
191508	P2.2	FL170 ↑	191	37°2' / 97°30'	still clear above here North
1918	Interrupt	FL190			Held by air traffic
191943	P2.3	FL190 ↑	187	36°54' / 97°30'	still clear above
1924		FL240 ↑		36°36' / 97°30'	Cl overhead <u>just</u> above
1926		FL265 ↑	187	36°24' / 97°30'	clear overhead now
	Interrupt	FL330		36°42' / 97°30'	In clear slot above + below
194432	R2.1	FL350	352	36°24' / 97°30'	194445 Sonde release
					194543 "
					194716 "
					194952 "
1949					Some wisps of cloud below
195418	end R2.1	FL350			
195841	start R2.2	"	283		195855 clear below
2004	R2.2	FL350	188	36°42' / 97°30'	Few clouds below at times
2008	"	"	"	36°24' / 97°30'	200543 sonde release
					↳ clouds below Ci patches
201422	end R2.2	"		35°42' / 97°30'	clear, but clouds below nearby
201832	R2.3	FL350	351	36°6' / 97°30'	Cu-type clouds below 20:20
2027	"	"	352	36°54' / 97°30'	Over more extensive cloud below
203057	end R2.3	"		37°18' / 97°30'	Relatively clear at this N. end
	P3	FL350 ↓			
205145	end P3	FL145			
~2100	Land	Oklahoma City for refuel			

~221930 T/O Oklahoma City for transit home

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 283

Date: 16/4/07	Operator: papj	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
170755	70	0.1														P1	
1712	60	0.1															
171318	30	0.08														050	
171734	700	0.09														030	
171808																End p1	
171841	500	0.09														Start run 1.1	
1721	500	0.09															
1724	400	0.09															
1727	400	0.09															
1730	450	0.09															
1733	400	0.09															
1736	500	0.09															
174101	600	0.09														End run 1.1	
174545	550	0.09														Start run 1.2	
1750	600	0.09															
1753	600	0.09															
1756	400	0.09															
1759	430	0.09															
1802	450	0.09															
1805	400	0.09															
1808	500	0.09															
181216	500	0.09														End run 1.2	
181550	500															Start run 1.3	
182715	500	0.09														End 1.3	
182824	450	0.09														Start 1.4	
182921	500	0.09														End run 1.4	
1833	450	0.08														Start run 1.5	
1836	400	0.09															
1839	400	0.09															
184625	500	0.09														End run 1.5	
185140	450	0.09														P2	
185255	440	0.09														030	
191843	20	0.08														P 2.3	
192040	20	0.06														210	
	10	0.07														250	
	10	0.08														280	
	5	0.07														310	
195822	10	0.08														Start run 2.2	
2000	10	0.08															
2004	5	0.1															
2006	5	0.1															
2011	10	0.09															
201402																End run	
201832	10	0.08														Start run	
2029	20	0.07															
203057																End run	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B283 **T/O:** 155300
Date of flight: 16/4/07 **Land:** 233746

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	No	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to = 205713 2dproc files present yes *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records yes</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	y	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzorov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	n	<p>Last Nevzorov Vane busted</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B283 **T/O:** 155300
Date of flight: 16/4/07 **Land:** 233746

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	y	Min size =1 Vol flow rate = 1.0 155300 233800
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_proccasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_proccasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp' ii). WAVE> exit	y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	y	X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	y	Merged OK?


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14:29:15.60 --- - - - -
14:29:15.60 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:29:15.60 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:29:15.60 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B283
14:29:15.60 --- - - - -
14:29:41.98 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:29:47.64 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:29:56.36 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:30:09.37 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.
14:30:13.59 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:30:19.73 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:30:27.23 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:30:33.18 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:30:49.67 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
14:30:53.98 SWS - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
14:31:00.53 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
14:31:05.85 USH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
14:31:11.26 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
14:31:15.44 LSH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
14:31:20.96 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:31:20.96 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:31:24.36 SWS - - - - Idling
14:31:25.12 USH - - - - Idling
14:31:42.24 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:31:42.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:31:50.24 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:31:57.30 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:31:57.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:31:57.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:32:00.81 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:32:01.11 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:32:07.93 LSH - - - - Idling
14:32:09.05 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:32:15.71 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
14:32:20.31 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
14:32:26.66 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
14:33:31.45 --- - - - - *** Start up provided no problems. Believe
                    time problems on B282 was due to bad horace
                    start up.

15:22:17.66 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
15:22:24.55 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
15:22:28.53 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:22:28.63 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:22:28.63 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:22:31.67 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:22:32.39 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:22:38.92 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:22:50.15 --- - - - - *** sws head aft for take off
15:23:26.99 SWS - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
15:56:09.58 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:56:17.51 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:56:21.58 USH - - - 150 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
15:56:26.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:56:27.02 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:56:27.02 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:56:28.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:56:29.30 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:56:37.22 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:10:59.81 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
16:11:21.85 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
16:11:27.07 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
16:11:30.56 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:11:35.98 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
16:12:05.33 USH - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
16:12:11.77 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
16:12:13.93 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

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16:12:14.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:12:14.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:12:15.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:22.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:24.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:41.21	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
16:12:46.61	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
16:12:52.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:12:56.72	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 250ms.
16:12:57.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:51.57	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:15:56.55	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
16:16:03.79	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
16:16:08.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:09.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:09.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:13.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:16:14.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:16:20.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:16:21.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:16.63	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
16:25:20.60	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
16:25:27.84	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:25:34.46	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
16:25:37.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:45.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:24.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** transit through 5/8 cil and 2/8 as2
16:31:18.37	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 400ms.
16:31:25.59	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:31:26.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:27.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:27.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:32.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:35.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:37.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:01.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:01.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:01.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:07.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:09.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:11.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:42:15.67	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 250ms.
16:42:18.67	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 200ms.
16:42:24.71	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 50ms.
16:42:31.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:42:34.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:49:09.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:09.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:09.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:49:12.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:49:14.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:49:20.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:05:19.83	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:05:35.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** ready for start of run 1.1
17:05:53.68	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 400ms.
17:06:02.46	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
17:06:08.90	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
17:06:13.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:13.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:13.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:18.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:19.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:20.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:24.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:08:15.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile descent 1 170755
17:18:40.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.1
17:18:47.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:47.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:47.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

17:18:52.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:53.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:58.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:08.93	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:19:10.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:15.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:47.27	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
17:19:50.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:00.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:05.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** over arable land and small lakes
17:21:39.92	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:21:44.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:54.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:16.72	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:24:20.22	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:24:22.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:26.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:55.40	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:24:59.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:59.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:59.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:03.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:04.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:10.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:02.29	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:28:14.58	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
17:28:19.96	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:28:28.26	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
17:28:31.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:31.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:31.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:36.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:39.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:42.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:01.81	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:30:06.91	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
17:30:11.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:11.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:11.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:14.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:16.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:22.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:35:14.65	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:35:20.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:35:20.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:35:21.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:35:24.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:35:26.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:35:31.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:35:39.78	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:35:43.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:35:53.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:41:02.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:41:02.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:41:02.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:41:06.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:41:08.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:41:13.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:41:18.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.1 174101
17:43:18.85	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:43:34.02	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
17:44:47.44	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
17:44:51.96	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:44:58.72	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 350ms.
17:45:03.64	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
17:45:07.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:45:07.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:45:07.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:45:07.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

17:45:13.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:45:15.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:45:18.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:45:58.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.2 174545
17:46:03.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:04.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:04.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:09.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:46:12.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:46:15.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:46:45.89	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
17:46:50.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:46:58.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:49:56.75	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:50:02.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:12.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:16.46	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:50:19.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:29.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:37.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:47.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:48.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:49.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:49.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:54.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:50:57.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:51:00.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:51:34.71	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:51:53.79	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
17:51:59.06	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
17:52:04.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:04.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:05.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:09.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:10.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:52:15.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:28.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:32.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:37.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:55:40.30	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:55:42.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:55:46.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:13.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:14.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:14.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:18.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:19.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:24.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:00.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:03:00.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:03:00.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:03:04.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:05.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:10.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:59.33	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
18:05:02.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:05:05.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:08:20.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:08:20.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:08:21.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:08:23.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:08:26.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:08:31.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:24.64	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:11:28.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:38.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:15.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:15.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:15.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

18:12:18.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:21.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:25.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:54.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.2 181216
18:16:23.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.3 181550
18:16:47.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws still at 174 aft
18:16:50.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:16:50.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:16:50.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:16:53.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:16:56.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:17:00.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:17:50.86	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:17:56.25	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
18:17:59.91	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
18:18:04.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:04.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:04.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:09.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:12.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:15.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:39.24	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
18:19:43.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:19:51.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:22:06.84	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:22:10.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:22:20.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:23:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:23:13.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:23:13.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:23:18.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:23:21.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:23:24.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:27:20.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:20.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:20.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:25.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:27:28.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:27:30.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:28:06.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.3
18:28:15.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 182715
18:28:34.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.4 182824
18:29:35.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.4 182921
18:29:40.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:29:40.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:29:40.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:29:46.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:48.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:51.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:33:11.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.
18:33:11.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:12.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:12.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:17.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:33:20.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:33:22.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:33:29.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.5 183300
18:35:44.41	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
18:35:48.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:35:56.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:38:33.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:38:33.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:38:34.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:38:39.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:38:42.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:38:43.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:40:26.01	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:40:30.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:40:41.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:41:03.29	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
18:41:06.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:14.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:21.39	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
18:41:28.66	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:41:30.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:35.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:37.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:37.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:37.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:42.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:42.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:47.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:43:03.31	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
18:43:11.11	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
18:43:19.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:43:24.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:02.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:03.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:03.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:08.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:08.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:13.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:46:25.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:46:25.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:46:25.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:46:30.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:46:31.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:46:36.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:46:43.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.5 184625
19:29:12.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:12.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:12.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:18.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:18.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:23.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:30:10.00	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 400ms.
19:30:13.54	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
19:30:17.23	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
19:30:21.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:30:29.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:34:22.55	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:34:26.79	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 150ms.
19:34:31.94	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
19:34:36.30	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
19:34:40.98	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
19:34:51.40	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
19:34:59.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:34:59.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:34:59.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:03.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:05.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:09.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:42:38.14	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
19:42:47.98	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
19:42:50.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:50.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:51.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:55.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:42:56.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:43:01.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:37.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:37.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:37.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:44:41.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:42.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:47.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:45:26.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.0 193432
19:49:38.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

19:49:38.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:49:39.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:49:43.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:49:44.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:49:49.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:23.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:23.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:23.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:28.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:29.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:34.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:56:12.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2.0 195418
19:58:45.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:58:45.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:58:45.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:58:49.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:58:50.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:58:55.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:59:25.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.2 195841
19:59:32.73	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 350ms.
19:59:37.62	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
19:59:41.48	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
19:59:46.86	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
19:59:50.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:01.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:02:29.56	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
20:02:33.54	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
20:02:36.98	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
20:02:40.47	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
20:02:43.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:02:44.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:02:44.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:02:44.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:02:49.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:02:52.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:02:54.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:03:31.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:05:09.33	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
20:05:23.78	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
20:05:30.18	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
20:05:33.91	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
20:05:37.91	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
20:05:41.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:05:41.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:05:41.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:05:45.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:05:46.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:05:51.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:06:40.82	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
20:06:45.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:06:49.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:09:04.13	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
20:09:07.30	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
20:09:11.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:09:11.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:09:11.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:09:15.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:09:16.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:09:22.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:14:19.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:14:19.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:14:20.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:14:24.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:14:24.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:14:30.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:14:39.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2.2 201422
20:18:35.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:18:36.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:18:36.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

20:18:40.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:18:41.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:18:46.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:18:55.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.3 201832
20:20:15.62	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
20:20:18.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:20:29.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:24:09.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:24:09.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:24:09.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:24:14.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:24:14.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:24:19.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:25:32.03	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
20:25:36.57	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
20:25:42.77	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
20:25:47.17	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
20:25:51.12	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
20:25:55.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:26:03.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:27:17.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:27:17.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:27:18.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:27:23.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:27:25.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:27:28.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:27:30.21	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
20:27:35.21	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
20:27:39.26	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
20:27:44.13	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
20:27:46.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:27:50.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:31:00.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:31:00.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:31:01.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:31:04.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:31:06.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:31:11.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:31:23.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 2.3 203057
20:37:41.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to aft for landing
20:42:14.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** no further runs so end of science for sws
20:42:18.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:42:18.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:42:19.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:42:22.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:42:23.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:42:29.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:42:34.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:42:37.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:42:39.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

0800 →

ARIES flight log			Flight: B283	page 1 of
Date: 16/04/07	Operator(s): Joss	Res:	Gain A:2 B: 2	
Loc./Notes: Flying over Oklahoma ARM sight				

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
171802	Run 1	1/60	CBB	CSD	70.74	30.52	
171932	" "	1/60	HBB	CSD	30.52	30.66	70.74
172034	" "	600/1	CSD	Ncd			70.74 Dodni star data run.
		1/60	CBB				
		1/60	HBB				
172202	Run 1	600/1	Ncd	CSD	70.74	30.36	Started OK.
172718	" "	1/60	CBB	CSD	70.75	30.72	
172755	" "	1/60	HBB	CSD			
172840	" "	120/1	Zen	open	70.74	30.53	
172950	" "	480/1	Ncd	CSD	71.05	30.74	
173421	" "	600 /60	CBB	CSD	70.96	30.64	
173500	" "	600 /60	HBB	CSD	70.97	30.74	
173542	" "	600/1	Ncd	CSD	70.94	30.58	
174102	and R1-1	1/60	CBB	CSD	70.84	30.69	
174144	" "	1/60	HBB	CSD	71.05	30.66	
174184			CBB	CSD			
174403	"	1/60	CBB	CSD	71.08	31.01	
174444		1/60	HBB	CSD	70.77	31.24	
174539	R1-2	600/1	Zen	open	70.74	30.76	
175056	R1-2	1/60	CBB	CSD			
175138		1/60	HBB	CSD			
175178	" "	600/1	Ncd	CSD	71.05	30.80	Abou 175230
175756	" "	1/60	CBB	"	70.76	30.73	
175930	" "	1/60	HBB	"	70.88	30.85	
175918	" "	600/1	Ncd	"			
180420	" "	1/60	CBB	"	71.04	30.62	
180501	" "	1/60	HBB	"	70.77	30.98	
180558	" "	600/1	Ncd	"	70.85	30.67	
181109	" "	1/60	CBB	"	70.91	30.84	
181142	" "	1/60	HBB	"	70.72	30.97	
181359	" "	1/60	CBB	"	70.88	30.70	
1811.00	1/1.1	HRR			71.29	26.24	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13283

page 2 of

Date: 16/4/07

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
181521	R1-3	600/1	Zen	open	7043	30-18	WISS7 run above
182030	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd			
182105	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	71	31-75	
182148	u u	600/1	Zen	open	7057	31-36	
182655	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd	7090	32-37	
182733	u u	1/16	HBB	clsd	7099	32-34	
182811							
183157	R1-5	1/60	CBB	clsd	7104	31-58	
183245	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	7088	31-25	
183330	u u	600/1	Zen	open	7043	30-61	
183839	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd	7094	32-21	
183913	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	7094	32-07	
183955	u u	600/1	Zen	open	7062	31-63	
184504	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd	7109	32-7	
184545	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	7090	32-87	
194435	R1-1	1/60	CBB	clsd	7071	30-2	
194526	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd			
194610	u u	480/1	Nwd	clsd	7082	30-72	Nwd-s for 1st run!
194858	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd	7066	30-47	
194926	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd			ready for overpass
195014	u u	600/1	Nwd	clsd	7067	30-60	over fly @ 1951 z. finished
195511	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd	7075	30-64	cen
195551	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	7071	30-49	
195732	R2-2	480/1	Nwd	clsd	7058	31-30	
200135	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd			
200209	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	7037	30-60	
200250	u u	20/1	Zen	open			
200410	u u	360/1	Nwd	clsd	7096	30-47	
200725	u u	1/60	CBB	clsd	7045	30-48	
200918	u u	1/60	HBB	clsd	7044		
					7046	30-5	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	16/04/07	Flight	B283	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	JIAVEX		
Departure	Ellington		Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	1330ish
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290	Cold	285		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	NOT OPERATED					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	14:16:00	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	287.7
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	40	32	38	39	42

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	15:43:17

*15:59:58 medium is offline
h-optic aborted.

Changed optical disks & restarted h-optic @ 16:04

45108/1728/720/32

53424/2052/9120/352 16:41

h-optic DRS data to disk

h-optic_1 Checks optical disk space.

S61 error count on current optical disk (#2)

On initial descent seat belt sign switched on @ 17kft. ~ 17:01

3017 102a.

17:22 - CPS data record medium is offline 172312.

New optic @ 1724 1361 errors on disk (#3).

TWC fixed itself @ 1755ish

CO zero @ FL330. ~ 6.73 ie bottomed out.

23:30 ETA Oklahoma.

15 53
20 59 30

221928

233746

Flight:

B283

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:32:53

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

17/04/2007 01:13:55

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B283

Date: 16 April 2007

Instruments

1. h_optic aborted after take off had to reload a new optical disk
- 2.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 16/04/07

Flight No: B283

Pre-Flighter: JT UITHORE ©

Item	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	NO-OVERRIDE LOCK ON INSTR. BROKEN
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT FITTED @ THE PRESENT TIME
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	SWITCHES ON NOT LOGGING
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NOPH	KEYS CHANGED, OLD ONE ON CHAIN BUCKLE SPARE FITTED.	DAVE TUDORMAN

External Checks overleaf →

POINT OF INTEREST - WHO IS RESPONSIBLE FOR PSAP START UP, APPEARS TO BE MISSED BY PRE-FLIGHT & FM NOTES.

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> <input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	H631 OFF H 374 490 ON
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	OFF
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	N/A
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

Flight Manager's Data Processing Status

Flight No: B283

Date of flight: 16-4-07

Flight Manger:

Mfd data must be backed up within a week.

If it can't be done by the Cloud Physics Operator in that time the **FM must back it up**

<u>On day of flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Update Database & Note BBR Fit	Database	15.4.07
Create Fltcons & check BBR fit	Option 9	16.4.07
Transfer & process Data	Option 2	
Ftp qldata to BADC	project_spaces/faam/quicklook	
Check Rawdata	flight_plot	
Raw data to BADC	Option 7	
Copy & Convert Fltsumm file	Copy from optical to fltsumm directory Set def fltsumm run tarexec:convert_summ	
Edit Fltsumm/ send to BADC	Option 10	
Copy Flight logs	Flight Logs	
Download photos, clear camera & email Doug	To Flight Logs and Turb Probe Photos	
Ftp CGPS.bin file to BADC	project_spaces/faam/javad_gps	U/S
Check Mfddata	flight_plot	

<u>On day after flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Ftp PSAP to FLOODS	Bnnn_psap_data	
Merge PSAP into mfddata	wave .run mergepsap bnnn_mfda (b,c)	
Record mfd changes	edit mfddata:mfddata.txt	
NETCDF to BADC	Option 4	
Upload .nc from BADC	To USB stick (WS_FTP Pro)	
Data quality check	Run Checkg on Linux pc	
Ftp file to BADC	core_faam_yyyymm dd_r0_bnnn_quality.txt	
Print out quality file	put in Faults Book	
Backup raw data to optical	Option 6	
Backup mfd if Cloud Physics Operator can't	MFD Backup Instructions.doc	
Ftp mfd to BADC	Not yet set up	Watch this space
Video tapes to cupboard	Video Tape Log	
Complete & save this form	Data Processing Logs	

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B283:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP	Not operated on this flight
Wet Nephelometer	Not operated on this flight
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x For/Downward Facing Cameras

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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